

Do Brazilian Engineering Professors Do Engineering Education Research in Active Learning? A Case Study

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Abstract

While in countries like Brazil, the concern is still the training of instructors in the use of active learning strategies and methods, in countries such as the United States, Denmark, Sweden, Australia, for at least two decades, research has been placed at the service of teaching and teacher professional development and projects are developed so that research in Engineering Education is carried out with greater rigor. In this context, this research work aims to evaluate a set of interventions presented at the 43rd edition of the Brazilian Congress in Engineering Education (COBENGE), from the year 2015, because of the theme of the event: "Active Learning: Collaborative Engineers for a Competitive World. Thirty-six papers presented in this edition of COBENGE and that were related to active learning were analyzed to determine whether they are papers that address interventions such as an effective teaching (ET), a scholarly teaching (ST), a scholarship of teaching and learning (SoTL) or an engineering education research (EER) work. Our results show that from the 36 papers analyzed 25 are ET, 1 is ST, 2 are SoTL, 4 are EER works, and 4 could not be characterized in any of the levels. We present and discuss the approach built for the analysis performed based on the characteristics pointed out by the literature for ET, ST, SoTL and EER. It is worth pointing out that ST and SoTL are concepts little known to the Brazilian EE community. This research work is a starting point to evaluate the state of engineering education research in Active Learning in Brazil.

Keywords: Active Learning; Effective Teaching; Scholarly Teaching; Scholarship of Teaching and Learning; Engineering Education Research.

1 Introduction

According to de Graaff and Christensen (2004), active learning (AL) and Engineering Education (EE) are a perfect match, and thus engineering professors can be expected to employ active learning strategies and methods in their classes and courses. After all, the engineer must be educated to design and create solutions to practical real-world problems. Over the past two decades, research has shown that students prefer classes with active learning strategies and methods over traditional classes and that the adoption of AL instructional practices in STEM courses results in improvements in student learning, contributes to decrease dropout rates and reduce the performance gap between different student populations (McConnell et al., 2017; Freeman et al., 2014). In these research works, student performance was also evaluated and it was found that many AL strategies are comparable to traditional classes in promoting content mastery, but superior to promoting student skills and competence development (Freeman et al., 2014; Kay & MacDonald, 2016).

Unfortunately, even today, in many engineering schools in Brazil, the dominant pedagogy remains "chalk and talk" and curricula with a few project courses and laboratory practices, which are not enough to develop the skills desired by the world of work. In Brazil, both the possibilities and the challenges related to EE are debated by the participants of the Brazilian Congress in Engineering Education (COBENGE), which is considered the most important forum for reflection on EE in Brazil. The event is annually promoted by the Brazilian Association of Engineering Education (ABENGE), with the objective of bringing together schools and instructors to, together with government agencies and other entities interested in EE, share experiences, promote debates and propose strategies to train professionals increasingly more qualified to meet the country's needs.

Considering the obvious need for stronger actions regarding the creation of engineering programs that prepare engineers in tune with the problems of the 21st century, the Active Learning Working Group in

Engineering Education (GTAAEE¹) was created during COBENGE 2014. The GTAAEE has as main objectives: to disseminate the knowledge generated in active learning in engineering education (ALEE); to promote the creation of a research network in ALEE in Brazil; to foster the formalization of research groups in the area, in the most diverse engineering schools; and to promote the training of teachers to design AL environments (GTAAEE, 2022).

In 2019, seeking to update data on the use of AL strategies and methods in Brazil, previously surveyed by Oliveira, Pinto & Santos (2017), some GTAAEE researchers presented a study, from a systematic mapping, of articles published in the proceedings of COBENGE on AL strategies and methods from 2007 to 2019 (Pinto et al., 2019). The results obtained have shown an exponential growth in the number of publications of ALEE-related articles in COBENGE. This reveals the increasingly intense search by instructors and researchers for a teaching process focused on the development of skills and competencies.

In countries such as the United States, Denmark, Sweden, Australia, EE and research in EE are very advanced. For example, while in countries like Brazil, the concern is still the training of instructors in the use of AL strategies and methods, in the United States and in the aforementioned countries, for at least two decades, research has been placed at the service of teaching and teacher professional development and projects are developed so that research in EE is carried out with greater rigor (Shuman, & Besterfield-Sacre, 2019; Borrego & Bernhard, 2011; Streveler, Borrego & Smith, 2007).

Also, in 2019, the new National Curriculum Guidelines (BRASIL, 2019) for Engineering programs in Brazil were published, and it is believed that their implementation is a unique opportunity for more programs to have their curricula designed for competency-based training once and for all, which inevitably demands the incorporation of AL strategies and methods so that these curricula are, in fact, executed in their essence.

Allied to this, one must consider that, researching and reflecting on what one does in the classroom and then sharing it with peers is not a common practice among engineering professors. One of the reasons why this kind of research is often underestimated is that EE is not considered a research area in Brazil. Although the professors are teachers, they are not researchers in teaching and learning. For the most part, they are not trained in pedagogical methods, or self-identified with the professional community dedicated to research in education. Although the engineering professor may wish to engage in educational research, more often than not, he or she gets frustrated and gives up because they have no idea where to start. This becomes clear in the evaluation process of the papers at COBENGE. The great majority of the papers presented at the event do not present well-defined educational objectives, nor research objectives, and some do not even mention the term "engineering education".

In this context, and based on the objectives of GTAAEE, researchers of the group started a research, whose main objective was beyond the survey of the number of papers related to the application of AL strategies and methods, to determine the nature of the pedagogical interventions reported in the papers presented at COBENGE and to determine how much of these papers are research papers, minimally rigorous, in EE. Thus, this research paper aims to evaluate a set of interventions presented at the 43rd edition of COBENGE, held in the year 2015, due to the event's theme: "Active Learning: Collaborative Engineers for a Competitive World", a suitable starting point to evaluate the state of engineering education research in Active Learning in Brazil. Thirty-six papers presented at this edition of COBENGE, and which were related to AL, were analyzed to determine whether they are papers that address interventions such as effective teaching (ET), scholarly teaching (ST), scholarship of teaching and learning (SoTL), or research in engineering education (EER).

It is important to point out that research in engineering education starts with experiences of effective teaching (ET) and as the research becomes more mature, it progresses to ST, SoTL and EER. In other words, we can consider that ET, ST and SoTL are progressive levels of maturity of EER.

The following topics are presented in this article: a brief theoretical framework for ET, ST, SoTL and EER, the research methodology employed, the results and some final considerations.

¹ in this paper, the acronym used will be the acronym in Portuguese.

2 Theoretical Framework

In this section, the goal is to distinguish reports of pedagogical experiences from research associated with pedagogical interventions and from more complex research in EE. To this end, a brief description of the EER levels named ET, ST, SoTL will be given, and the basic principles of more complex EER will be presented.

2.1 ET (Effective Teaching)

An Effective Teaching intervention requires the use of good content and good teaching methods and tends to promote desirable learning outcomes. Kipper & Rütman (2012) point out models and strategies for Effective teaching in order to provide successful learning and the development of critical thinking in engineering students. They agree with Eggen and Kauchak (2006) that mastery of four types of knowledge by instructors is essential: (i) knowledge of content - what to teach; (ii) pedagogical content knowledge - how to teach a certain content; (iii) general pedagogical knowledge – understanding of general principles of instruction and classroom management; and (iv) knowledge of learners and learning – instructor’s ability to adapt their instruction based on what learners already know. Thus, when the intent is to characterize an Effective Teaching intervention, these elements should be identified in the teaching practice, through an assessment of student satisfaction, peer observation appraisal, self-reflection, among others.

2.2 ST (Scholarly Teaching)

A Scholarly Teaching intervention is nothing more than academic teaching. It implies the adoption of an academic approach to teaching, just as it is adopted for other areas of knowledge. It requires research and includes reflection. The instructor needs to have expertise in teaching and learning, to experiment with new pedagogical strategies and methods, to study and apply the literature on teaching and learning in the courses, to reflect on his/her teaching. According to Richlin (2001), "Scholarly teachers are those who consult the literature, select and apply appropriate information to guide the teaching-learning experience, conduct systematic observations, analyze the outcomes, and obtain peer evaluation of their classroom performance".

2.3 SoTL (Scholarship of Teaching and Learning)

A Scholarship of Teaching and Learning intervention involves high level academic teaching and learning. It addresses university teaching and learning by investigating student learning in the classroom. According to Rütman & Saar (2017):

In general, SoTL includes rigorous, systematic, and evidence-based study of student learning; the understanding and improvement of student learning and/or teaching practice; commitment to disciplinary and/or interdisciplinary peer review and appropriate public dissemination; impact beyond a single course, program, or institution – advancing the field of teaching and learning to build collective knowledge and ongoing improvement. (Rütman & Saar, 2017, p.214)

It emphasizes the identification and definition of a problem and demands systematic collection of evidence that will be the results from which conclusions will be drawn (Dewar, Bennet & Fisher, 2018). The instructor needs to have knowledge of the disciplinary content, of effective pedagogical practices, and of discipline-specific pedagogical practices. According to Streveler, Borrego & Smith (2007), the involvement in SoTL usually begins with faculty's interest in how their own students are learning in their classrooms, and the main purpose of SoTL is to improve learning by improving teaching. " The results of a Scholarship of Teaching and Learning intervention should add knowledge to the literature on teaching and learning and contribute to the scientific productivity of the faculty.

2.4 EER (Engineering Education Research)

EER goes beyond the classroom and student learning and consists of the development of more rigorous studies related to EE (Streveler, Borrego & Smith, 2007). The ultimate goal of EE is, among several, to influence classroom practice and policies for conducting engineering programs from its findings. In EER, the researcher focuses on the "why" and the "how" of the educational phenomena involved in EE. The researcher identifies relevant, meaningful research questions; reviews the literature, links to appropriate theory, uses appropriate

research methods aligned with the research question, interprets the data, disseminates the results in a generalized way. In general, EER demands a set of methods and processes that can be seen as different from the usual research in specific engineering disciplines. Borrego (2007, p. 99) claims that "research [in EER] is fundamentally different from engineering research". This turns out to be a hindrance to the development of EER, since most engineering professors lack familiarity with literature in the field of education and with research methodologies suitable for educational studies (Froyd & Lohmann, 2014).

Having presented the main characteristics related to ET, ST, SoTL and EER, the next section will present the methodological procedures developed in this research.

3 Methodological Procedures

The present research is characterized as qualitative research. It investigates the nature of papers presented at COBENGE 2015, regarding the classification of these papers as being pedagogical interventions, such as ET, ST, SoTL, or research in EE. The qualitative character of this research is explained by Deslauriers (1991, p. 58) when he says that "The purpose of the sample is to produce in-depth and illustrative information: whether it is small or large, what matters is that it is capable of producing new information."

The survey, which identified the 36 studies involving AL strategies and methods published in the annals of COBENGE 2015 and analyzed in this work, was carried out by Pinto et al. (2020) with the main objective of, as mentioned before, verifying the growth of AL in EE in Brazil in the period from 2007 to 2019 in COBENGE's proceedings.

After identifying the papers, their abstracts were read for an initial classification in terms of ET, ST, SoTL, and EER. Subsequently, a more in-depth reading of each of the papers was necessary for the final classification presented in this paper. For the classification into ET, ST, SoTL or EER, the characteristics described in sections 2.1, 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4 were taken into consideration. The researchers randomly divided the 36 papers into two groups of 18 papers. Each analyzed 18 papers. In case of doubt, the work was read by the other researcher, and this second reading was followed by a discussion between the two researchers. The characteristics described in sections 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, and 2.4 were sought in each of the papers. When found in the papers, these characteristics were highlighted and noted.

In the next section, the results obtained through the described procedures are presented and discussed.

4 Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the number of papers classified in each of the levels, namely ET, ST, SoTL or EER.

Table 1. Classification of papers in ET, ST, SoTL and EER levels.

ET	ST	SoTL	EER	Other
25	1	2	4	4

The general analysis of the classification shows an imbalance between the quantity of ET papers, which include experience reports, 69% of the total number of papers, and scientific research papers, which include the ST, SoTL and EER levels, and represent 19% of the total number of papers analyzed. In addition, 11% of the papers do not fall into any of the levels. The most relevant results for each level are presented and discussed below.

4.1 ET

COBENGE accepts two types of papers, "experience report" and "scientific research", however, there are no clear criteria for what is an "experience report". Of the 25 papers initially classified as ET, 72% focused on technical issues of the project/experiment developed, while 28% focused on the methods and strategies of ET. In both cases, there were papers with: evidence of student learning gains, mostly results of grades from evaluative activities, such as traditional tests; results from satisfaction surveys; and statements from the authors

that the learning was effective, although without verifiable data. These are all papers that claim to present an innovation in the classroom. However, as pointed out by Wankat, Felder, Smith, & Oreovicz (2002, p. 217), the evaluation of innovation is typically something like "We (the teachers) tried it and liked it, as did most of the students". Based on these characteristics, we defined the experience reports (ER) intervention as: descriptions of methods applied in the classroom and/or development of experiments or prototypes to support teaching. In general, the ER interventions do not present a consistent theoretical review of the AL strategies and methods nor do they provide criteria, data, or evidence of learning gains. In this sense, in this research, it was decided to formalize the ER level for the papers presenting these characteristics. From the 25 papers initially classified as ET, 18 papers were reclassified as ER, which means 50% of all 36 AL papers.

Among the six works classified as ET, we highlight the work of Guimarães et al. (2015), in which the authors describe an activity developed and coordinated by students of a group from the Tutorial Education Program, under faculty mentoring, directed to freshmen and inserted in the "Introduction to Electrical Engineering" course. From instructions and materials prepared by the students who organized the activity, teams assembled line following robots and, in the end, participated in a competition. It is worth mentioning that there are learning gains for all involved, students who are the organizers and freshmen, and that competitions of this type generate engagement and emotional involvement, contributing to the consolidation of new knowledge. The authors explain that the activity involves technical knowledge, mainly related to electronics, as well as attitudes such as proactivity, flexibility, tolerance to uncertainty, and skills such as teamwork, written and oral communication, planning, management and leadership. The results include team and participants' evaluation of the activity and the project, reflection on the technical and non-technical learning gains, and the paper also mentions agreement with the competencies expected and based on the National Curriculum Guidelines² and on ASIBEI³. The instrument mentioned for data collection is the questionnaire.

Analyzing in more detail the work of Guimarães et al. (2015), one realizes that experiments, team brainstorming, reflections, and non-formalized observations were carried out. It is possible to identify characteristics of action research and the interrelation between teaching, research, and extension. It is observed that there are numerous instruments that can be used to obtain evidence of effective teaching in addition to those already mentioned: interviews and focus groups; content analysis; experiments; case studies; multi-method studies and hybrid methods.

The paper highlights the competences exercised in each phase of the proposed activity, such as planning, elaboration, testing or execution, and this helps in the definition of learning indicators that can be used to analyze student performance and generate evidence for evaluating the results of a proposal. A review of the literature including similar experiences, greater care with methodological procedures regarding the strategies and methods of AL and the methods of data collection, as well as the evaluation of student performance, would elevate the work to the ST level.

4.2 ST

In the ST level, a single paper was identified (Spricigo, 2015), which presents the results of the application of the PBL method in a technical feasibility study of an industrial enterprise in a class of 17 students in a course of the Food Engineering program, replacing the traditional lectures previously held. The author presents the method adopted, in which an open problem divided into two parts was chosen. The methodology developed involved the presentation of the results and a debate with the class about the solution found by each team. To evaluate the students' motivation the Situational Motivation Scale (SIMS) was used. For the evaluation of learning gains, the grades of an individual written test on a problem-situation similar to the theme of the applied PBL were considered. Rubrics were used to correct the test. Results obtained with the use of the SIMS scale indicated a high level of intrinsic motivation and a low level of demotivation in the class during the PBL.

² National Curricular Guidelines for Engineering Courses, Resolution CNE/CES 11, of March 11, 2002. The New Curricular Guidelines, of April 24, 2019, are currently in effect.

³ Declaration of Valparaíso on Generic Competences of the Iberoamerican Engineer

However, extrinsic motivation, which indicates the execution of activities to obtain a reward, was representative. In the individual test results, 90% of the students met all rubrics. The author makes reflections based on the qualitative results of the teams and mentions gains in complexity in the issues discussed and in the role of the professor as mediator.

The main characteristics identified in the analyzed work are: adoption of academic approach to teaching; use of hybrid methods; experimentation with new techniques; application of literature on teaching and learning in the course; reflection on teaching; evidence-based study of student learning; analysis of understanding and improvement of learning; impact on a single course.

Although Spricigo's (2015) work presents the characteristics of an ST, the application of the PBL method was not developed considering all the stages of the method, nor the evaluative instruments usually used when applying PBL, for example, peer and self-assessment. Recommendations for a paper like Spricigo's (2015) to be classified as a SoTL also involve sharing experiences and reflections on the results with professors from other courses and programs; for it to be classified as an EER, it would need to broaden the scope of application of AL methods and strategies, include real problems involving companies and/or professionals in the field, and/or promote continuous improvement of the results.

4.3 SoTL

In the SoTL level, the works of Chinaglia & Santos (2015) and Gomes, Lima & Bianchini (2015) were identified. In the first, the authors present quantitative results on the introduction of AL strategies for large physics classes. The research involves an experimental group of 247 students who participated in the new teaching proposal, a control group with 124 students submitted to the traditional teaching method, and 3 instructors responsible for each group. The new methodological proposal includes lecture, demonstrative simulation, conceptual test, and group work to solve problems. The traditional method consists of lecture and exercise solving by the instructor. The authors used the mechanics baseline test, known worldwide as the "Force Concept Inventory" (Hestenes, Wells, & Swackhamer, 1992) to assess the prior knowledge of all students and found a leveling of the classes. The effectiveness of the developed methodology is verified by comparing the average scores of the students' performance on 3 tests and also their attendance in class. Besides the improvement in the average grades, the experimental class presented a lower rate of absences. After this experience, the proposal started to be applied in 100% of the physics courses, involving all the physics instructors of the institution. Also in this paper, despite the good results achieved, a certain lack of knowledge by the authors about the AL strategies is noted. In this particular context, when using conceptual tests in the development of the classes, the authors do not mention the Peer Instruction strategy, famous for its excellent results in learning gains in physics courses, and whose central point is the conceptual test conceived by Mazur (1997).

In the second paper, Gomes, Lima & Bianchini (2015) investigate the learning gains of 25 freshmen of an engineering program, by means of an intervention carried out with the Jigsaw method of cooperative learning, as part of a doctoral research of the Graduate Studies Program in Mathematics Education of São Paulo's Pontifical Catholic University (PUC/SP). The chosen subject was the study of the line in two- and three-dimensional spaces. Five study themes were proposed, a final question and an individual evaluation question. They used as methods of data collection, observations and interviews. All five groups did well in the development of the activities. The authors infer that "the Jigsaw method of cooperative learning can allow students to move through other styles of mathematical thinking different from their preferred ones". It is observed in this paper the authors' deep knowledge of the Jigsaw method (Aronson, & Patnoe, 2010). This characteristic of the article may be associated with the fact that the research work is linked to the development of a doctoral thesis.

Common features of the papers are: good description of methodological procedures, including data collection methods; analysis of results; extrapolation from the classroom; systematic evidence-based study of student learning; the understanding and improvement of learning; engagement with disciplinary colleagues; impact on multiple courses.

An important issue to be considered in SoTL interventions is the focus on improving teaching and learning and contributing to faculty productivity. Thus, works of this nature are closely related to the existence of faculty

training programs. In Brazil, teacher training in engineering programs is still incipient, and most of the time, actions related to improving teaching are generally the teacher's own initiative or rare teacher training sessions.

4.4 EER

In the EER level, four papers were identified, which in common present theoretical review, describe the methodological procedures, including data collection methods; analyze the results from the data and demonstrate that the objectives were met. They certainly go beyond the classroom, however, a feature that draws attention is the fact that all of them address the Project-based learning (PjBL) method. Three papers are related to the organization of curricula of engineering programs, three are from Brazil and also three had explicit cooperation with the University of Minho (UMinho), not necessarily the same papers.

It is worth highlighting the work of Schlichting & Heinig (2015), from the Graduate Program in Education at the Regional University of Blumenau. The authors discuss the implications of AL regarding the uses of orality, reading and writing in the professional daily life in engineering. This is a qualitative research that involves discourse analysis from interviews conducted with students from the 7th semester of the Integrated Master in Industrial Engineering and Management at UMinho. The research brings a contextualization of the scenario studied at this university from the perspective of PLE (Project-Led Education) and also about its relationship with the world of work. The authors present a consistent theoretical framework as a basis for the analysis and discussion of the results. The methodological procedure is presented in a diluted form, throughout the text as the students' statements are interpreted from their experiences in the PLE and their first professional experiences. The authors attest to the need of inserting the student in realistic interaction practices and the importance of a spiral curriculum, in such a way as to allow the student to move from general knowledge to specialized knowledge. It is interesting to note that the authors' conclusion refers to Bruner's discovery learning in which the learner is exposed to the same topic in different ways and levels of depth.

Another work of interest is that of Santos and Silva (2015), which presents the experience of the first contact with the project-based learning method from the perceptions of freshmen of the computer engineering program at the State University of Feira de Santana, in northeastern Brazil. A questionnaire answered by 14 participants brings the students' impressions. In the first part, questions about satisfaction are raised; in the second part, the skills developed; in the third part the infrastructure is evaluated, and in the last part the overall satisfaction with the method is raised. Although it has been classified as an EER, from the analysis of this work it can be seen that the authors could have mentioned similar applications in the theoretical review in order to compare the results found with those in the literature and thus be able to better evaluate the contribution. Also, the PBL model used was not well clarified.

5 Final Remarks

A reflection on such a large quantity of papers (50% of the total, classified as ER) that only describe practices or procedures without effectively demonstrating the gains in student learning implies a greater attention to the training of engineering professors for EE issues. In many papers, gaps are observed about several important aspects of AL strategies and methods, such as the stages of application, the evaluation of learning when applying such a strategy/method, among others. It is essential that the instructor knows the AL strategy and/or method that he/she will use in the design of the learning environments in order to be able to choose which one will help in the development of the intended learning outcomes. Only then, the instructor will be able to develop a good ET intervention.

The very small number of papers classified as ST and SoTL is closely related to the fact that most engineering schools in Brazil are not supported by faculty training programs. The results of a survey conducted by the ABENGE's Teacher Training Working Group (Battistini & Mattasoglio, 2020) on the training of engineering instructors confirm that in most higher education institutions in Brazil there is no space for the training of

engineering instructors. This data also supports the significant amount of ER papers found in this research. It is worth pointing out that ST and SoTL are concepts little known to the Brazilian EE community.

In relation to the EER papers, this research did not expect a significant number of papers in this level, after all, COBENGE is a national event, and EER papers, in general, are submitted for publication in specialized journals. However, it was expected early stage EER papers or clippings from a more robust research project. Here, it is worth presenting a result reported by Williams (2018), in which he highlighted that in the period from 2015 to 2018, Brazilian researchers submitted 14 papers to the Journal of Engineering Education in different EE subjects. Nine of these papers were rejected upon submission, five were revised, and none of them were accepted for publication. Unfortunately, this result presented by Williams points to a certain unpreparedness of Brazilian engineering professors for EE research.

Although the analysis carried out was in articles from 2015 and, therefore, can be considered a little outdated, what matters is that this research considers the theme Active Learning addressed in 2015 in COBENGE and is, as far as is known, a first step to analyze the state of the art of engineering education research in AL in Brazil.

This research work should be extended to evaluate a more significant number of COBENGE papers on AL strategies and methods, in principle, from 2015 to 2021. The results presented here point to the need of a discussion to be developed within the EE community in Brazil. As actions to improve the scenario presented here, the GTAAEE is working to organize its symposium which will address the theme "Scholarship of Teaching and Learning" and to create a tutorial for the planning of ET type interventions to assist in the submission of papers to COBENGE.

This paper will be finished with the following statement:

"Changing practice in engineering education so that faculty members apply findings in engineering education research, education research, and research in the learning sciences to their practice in engineering classrooms is a major challenge for engineering education practice and research (Jamieson & Lohmann, 2012)"

because this statement masterfully describes the great challenge that engineering education research in Brazil still has to face.

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